

ENHANCEMENT ACTIVITIES IN GRADE 9 SCIENCE UTILIZING COLLABORATIVE APPROACH

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 27

Issue 3

Pages: 342-348

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2564

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14013576

Manuscript Accepted: 10-01-2024

Enhancement Activities in Grade 9 Science Utilizing Collaborative Approach

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Abstract

This study aimed to develop, validate, and determine the performance of the students using the enhancement activities based on the 2nd quarter most essential learning competencies (MELCS) in Science for grade 9 learners utilizing the collaborative approach at Teresa National High School (TNHS) in the School Year 2020-2021. This study used developmental, descriptive and experimental research design. The total enumeration or forty (45) Grade 9 students who were the respondents of this study were exposed to the developed enhancement activities. Fifteen (15) Science teachers who are teaching Chemistry subjects were asked to evaluate the developed enhancement activities. Based on the analyses and interpretation of data gathered, the developed enhancement activities in Science 9 utilizing the collaborative approach found out that the content, format and presentation and organization were very satisfactory. While present but very minimal minor errors must be fixed in terms of accuracy and up-to-datedness of information gathered. It was also found out that before the exposure to the developed enhancement activities in Science 9, a fair performance of the learners was seen while after the exposure to the materials, the performance of the learners becomes very satisfactory and outstanding. The data also revealed that there is significant difference on the level of performance of the grade 9 learners before and after exposure to the developed enhancement activities utilizing the collaborative approach since the computed probability values among all the competencies are lesser than 0.05 level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. Likewise, the developed enhancement activities for Science 9 utilizing collaborative approach met the criteria outlined in the LRMDS guidelines and received high praise from Science teachers, and may be beneficial for teaching. The learner-respondents performed well in the six competencies as reflected on the improvements showed between the pretest and posttest. Mastery can be seen on those improvements.

Keywords: *enhancement activities, science, collaborative approach*

Introduction

Considering that education is growing more global, and the learners are becoming increasingly diverse, the teachers are challenged to create and make learning have positive impacts on the learners. Certain teaching methods such as game-based learning are specifically designed to incorporate fun into the lesson. These approach, which may be especially beneficial for kinesthetic learners to learn best via hands-on activities through the conduct of more dynamic and entertaining classes.

One of the main components of the 21st century teachers want is to improve learners' learning through collaborative learning. This is when learners use complex methods to take their understanding of what they are learning to a whole new level. Learners using it are understanding higher levels rather than just memorizing math facts. They would have to understand the facts, infer them, and connect them to other concepts.

However, detailed studies show the complexity of the role of the teacher, especially teachers as implementers of the entire curriculum. Studies show that fundamental change takes time, especially when quality science education demands it. Changing classrooms to focus on student learning is no small task and will require the willingness and collaborative efforts of teachers, parents, the community, as well as the learners.

In February 2019, the Philippines joined the first Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM), a pen-and-paper large-scale assessment for learners conducted by the United Nations International Children's Fund (UNICEF). The results showed that 27 percent of Filipino pupils in Grade 5 were only able to recognize single words, while only 10 percent of them developed reading proficiency to allow their proper transition to secondary education.

The school performance results of the National Achievement Test (NAT) from School Year 2021-2022 in Science generally showed a mean percentage score range, which is interpreted as a lower average in different learning competencies measured and far behind the standard criterion by the Department of Education (DepEd) in terms of achievement level, which is 75% as the national target. In this pursuit, the enhancement activities in grade 9 Science utilizing a collaborative approach would help solve the poor performance in grade 9 science because the researcher could easily identify the cause and effects of the so-called hindrances for the positive and best learning that would resolve the said problems.

The researcher believed that enhancement activities in Science for grade 9 through a collaborative approach improve the interaction between learners and teachers as well as support active engagement in the learning process. The collaborative mastery approach would greatly help DepEd achieve its vision of actively engaging learners in the learning and teaching processes.

This was the basis on which the researcher formulated and conducted the enhancement activities in Science through a collaborative learning approach intended for grade 9 learners to develop and reinforce their potential to think critically and creatively, to create

generations of resilient learners, especially those who are at risk of falling below the comprehension level in the class.

Research Questions

The study aimed to develop, validate, and determine the effectiveness of the developed enhancement activities in Science for grade 9 utilizing the collaborative approach at Teresa National High School for the School Year 2020–2021. Particularly, the present study sought answers the following questions:

1. How are the enhancement activities in Science 9 utilizing collaborative approach developed?
2. How do the science teachers evaluate the developed enhancement activities in Science 9 utilizing the collaborative approach with respect to:
 - 2.1. content;
 - 2.2. format;
 - 2.3. presentation and organization; and
 - 2.4. accuracy and up-to-datedness of information?
3. What is the level of performance of the grade 9 learners before and after exposure to the developed enhancement activities in Science 9 utilizing the collaborative approach?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of performance of the grade 9 learners before and after exposure to the developed enhancement activities in Science 9 utilizing the collaborative approach?

Literature Review

Naar (2021) explained that an enrichment activity is classified as any activity that allows students to learn new things from new, often unexpected perspectives. Often, this involves interactive, hands-on tasks. After-school enrichment programs might offer activities related to yoga, cooking, sports, science, math, board games, art, and much, much more. Additionally, classroom debates, research projects, and field trips fall under the enrichment umbrella.

Marcos (2020) claim that enhancement activities is important to cope up with the current condition of the Science education in the Philippines. As mentioned, enhancement activities can also be defined as the name implies to cater the needs of learners unable to keep pace with the teaching-learning process in a normal classroom. This will act as safety valve for the students who are behind the expected level of achievement. Sansivero (2016) said that collaborative learning is one of the teaching approaches where students work in groups so as to understand a concept, create a product or solve a problem. Unlike individual learning, students engage with one another to ask for information, evaluate their ideas and monitor their work together.

Several researchers have recommended collaborative learning approaches to teaching metacognition that identify group discussions about the use of reading strategies as one critical feature of an intervention targeted at improving students' metacognition during reading. Evans and Cleghom (2022) points out that the attribute of the superior performance of students working in collaborative group settings is of higher quality of discourse observed among students working together. Students participating in cooperative learning expressed their ideas better in writing more able than did those who worked alone. Tambongco (2021) created and validated enhancement activities for grade 7 science. It was held at Morong National High School during the school year 2014-2015, with 50 students each section. According to the findings of the study, the produced enhancement activities in science were extremely efficient in teaching various learning areas such as cells to organisms, plant and animal cells, and microscopy. The study's findings indicated that the group exposed to created and verified enhancement activities in science performed much better in all learning areas than the group that did not use the enhancement activity.

According to Fakomogbon and Bolaji (2020), teachers use collaborative learning to facilitate learning and improve learners' performance. A variety of learning approaches can be accommodated by mobile learning. As a result, this study looked into the effects of collaborative learning styles on student performance in a mobile learning environment. The findings revealed that there were significant gains in the difference between students' pretest and posttest scores during the mobile learning experience, and the think-aloud-pair problem-solving technique is the most effective collaborative learning style. Furthermore, when compared to non-collaborative learning styles, all collaborative learning styles are more effective for learning in a mobile learning environment.

Furthermore, a recent study by Liang et al. (2021) investigated the impact of collaborative enhancement activities on student learning. The researchers found that collaborative enhancement activities can lead to significant improvements in student learning outcomes, including increased knowledge, skills, and engagement. The study also found that the effectiveness of collaborative enhancement activities is dependent on a number of factors, including the type of activity, the way it is implemented, and the students' prior knowledge and skills.

Methodology

Research Design

This study entitled Enhancement Activities in Grade 9 Science Utilizing Collaborative Approach used the descriptive research design to gather information and collect data on characteristics of group of people. The grade 9 learners' information in learning pattern in

this study were gathered through survey method using the questionnaire checklist. Developmental research was also used that refers to the process of investigating or tracking the improvement of grade 9 learners for a better understanding for what might need to consider for improvement so the pretest and posttest was used. This study also utilized the experimental method of research design for the researcher to determine the cause-and-effect relationship between variables to draw more reliable conclusion on findings whether the developed enhancement activities are effective or not during the implementation and administration on Grade 9 students in Teresa National High School in pre- determined duration.

Respondents

This study utilized total enumeration, the whole section which comprises of forty-five (45) learners were the respondents of this study. They were the ones who utilized the enhancement activities. Purposive sampling was used to determine the experts who evaluated the developed enhancement activities. Fifteen (15) Science teachers were asked to evaluate using the adapted questionnaire checklist from the LRMDS.

Instrument

The questionnaire-checklist was used in gathering data to determine the acceptability of the enhancement activities in terms of content, format, presentation and organization and accuracy and up to-datedness of information. The study also utilized pretest-posttest research design. This design enables the researcher to determine whether the developed enhancement activities in grade 9 science utilizing collaborative approach are effective or not during the implementation at Teresa National High School.

Procedure

The researcher determined first the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) as the basis of what will be the content of the enhancement activities.

To determine the evaluation of the experts on the developed enhancement activities in Science 9 utilizing the collaborative approach with respect to content, format, presentation and organization, and accuracy and up-to-datedness of information, the researcher adapted a questionnaire checklist from the LRMDS.

Pretest and Posttest were given to the Grade 9 learners to determine the level of performance before and after exposure to the developed enhancement activities in Science 9 utilizing the collaborative approach.

To determine the significant difference in the levels of performance of the grade 9 learners before and after exposure to the developed enhancement activities in Science 9 utilizing the collaborative approach, the dependent t-test was employed.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher herself explained and gave the informed consent to each participant before the conduct of the study. She ensured them that the information would be used with utmost confidentiality and within the purpose of the study only.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Development of the Enhancement Activities in Science 9 utilizing the Collaborative Approach

With the use of the Department of Education's 2020 Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) for Science 9, the researcher came up with the development of the enhancement activities utilizing a collaborative approach.

The researcher showed the planning and designing of the layout to demonstrate how the Enhancement Activities in Grade 9 Science Using Collaborative Approach were developed. This relates to accuracy, information updates, organization, and cooperative actions in each concept.

Collaborative Enhancement Activities, which were used to create the material, books, and online resources was used to gather the information needed to create the content, Canva and Google Images to create and generate the images for better understanding and to improve the material and add value to the information being presented.

In order to create the ideal layout and content for the enhancement activities, and that were free of errors to prevent learners from becoming confused, the researcher conducted a number of modifications. The researcher made note of every obvious mistake from the beginning of the layout to the very end, ensuring that mistakes were fixed, and fixes were made better.

The Enhancement Activities in Grade 9 Science Using Collaborative Approach were assessed for its acceptability in terms of content, format, organization, presentation, accuracy, and up-to-date information, and it was also assessed by the students' level of performance in science 9 using the material.

Having done with the development of the collaborative enhancement activities for Grade 9, the research has released the material for validation and evaluation. With the help of the adviser, the researcher used the Evaluation Template 6.4 or Refer to Guidelines and

Processes for LRMDs Assessment and Evaluation. This is the standard evaluation tool used by the Department of Education's Learning Resource Management and Development System in evaluating print resources such as self-learning modules.

Science Teachers Evaluation on the Developed Enhancement Activities in Science 9 Utilizing Collaborative Approach

Table 1. *Science Teachers Evaluation on the Developed Enhancement Activities in Science 9 Utilizing Collaborative Approach with Respect to its Content*

	<i>Content</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Content is suitable to the students' level of development.	3.37	Very Satisfactory
2.	Material contributes to the achievement of specific objectives of the subject area and grade/year level for which it is intended.	3.28	Very Satisfactory
3.	Material provides for the development of higher cognitive skills such as critical thinking, creativity, learning by doing, inquiry, problem solving etc.	3.45	Very Satisfactory
4.	Material is free from ideological, cultural, religious, racial and gender biases and prejudices.	3.39	Very Satisfactory
5.	Material enhances the development of desirable values and traits.	3.30	Very Satisfactory
6.	Materials have the potential to arouse the interest of the target reader.	3.67	Very Satisfactory
7.	Adequate warning/cautionary notes are provided in topics and activities where safety and health are concerned. (If applicable).	3.29	Very Satisfactory
	Overall	3.39	Very Satisfactory

The table shows that the science teachers found the enhancement activities in Science 9 to be very satisfactory in terms of its content with an overall mean of 3.39. It means that the content of the created instructional materials in Science 9 is appropriate for students' level of learning development. The findings imply that the instructional materials for learners in Science 9 contained clear content that enables the learners to understand the different topics.

It is in consonance with the findings of Selga (2013) in her study entitled "Scantiness of Instructional Materials in Senior High School: Basis for a Proposed Digital Instructional Archive" she found out that teaching materials is a generic term used to describe the resources teachers utilize to deliver instruction with ease and greater effectiveness. Regardless of their variation, these materials support learning content, allow students to engage in the concepts application and provide an opportunity for evaluation.

Table 2. *Science Teachers Evaluation on the Developed Enhancement Activities in Science 9 Utilizing Collaborative Approach with Respect to its Format in Prints*

	<i>Format</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
<i>Prints</i>			
1.	Size of letters is appropriate to the intended user.	3.67	Very Satisfactory
2.	Spaces between letters and words facilitate reading.	3.23	Very Satisfactory
3.	Font is easy to read.	3.00	Very Satisfactory
4.	Printing is of good quality (i.e. no broken letter, even density, correct alignment, properly placed screen registration)	3.45	Very Satisfactory
	Overall	3.34	Very Satisfactory

As seen in the table, the prints of the developed enhancement activities in science 9 have an overall mean value of 3.34 and verbally interpreted as very satisfactory. The findings imply that the instructional materials for learners in science 9 contained clear and concise format in prints that make the presentation more engaging to the learners that contributes to achievement of specific objectives.

In relation with the findings Sung & Wang (2013) on "Using Technology to Enhance Student Learning Experiences in Higher Education" This article explores the use of various technologies (e.g. clear simulations, interactive exercises) to enrich learning. It highlights the importance of user-friendly interfaces and clear prints and instructions for optimal engagement.

Table 3. *Science Teachers Evaluation on the Developed Enhancement Activities in Science 9 Utilizing Collaborative Approach with Respect to its Format in Illustrations*

	<i>Illustrations</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Simple and easily recognizable.	3.29	Very Satisfactory
2.	Clarify and supplement the text.	3.35	Very Satisfactory
3.	Properly labelled or captioned (if applicable)	3.32	Very Satisfactory
4.	Realistic/appropriate colors.	3.59	Very Satisfactory
5.	Attractive and appealing.	3.18	Very Satisfactory
6.	Culturally relevant.	3.60	Very Satisfactory
	Overall	3.39	Very Satisfactory

As seen in the table, the Illustrations of the developed enhancement activities in science 9 are found to be very satisfactory for the learners with an overall mean of 3.39. The format in terms of its illustrations for each topic guides the learners to the appropriateness of the enhancement activities intended for the learners. The findings shows that the instructional materials for learners in science 9 contained clear and concise format in illustrations promote understanding of the activity's goals in promoting effective learning.

This is in consonance with recent research "The Role of Illustrations in Science Education: A Meta-Analysis" (2023) by Tabiolo & Rogayan: This meta-analysis confirms the positive impact of illustrations on science learning, highlighting the importance of their relevance and coherence with the text

Table 4. *Experts Evaluation on the Developed Enhancement Activities in Science 9 Utilizing Collaborative Approach with Respect to its Format in Design and Layout*

<i>Design and Layout</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. Attractive and pleasing to look at.	3.54	Very Satisfactory
2. Simple (i.e., does not distract the attention of the reader)	3.42	Very Satisfactory
3. Adequate illustration in relation to text.	3.49	Very Satisfactory
4. Harmonious blending of elements. (e.g. illustration and text)	3.51	Very Satisfactory
Overall	3.49	Very Satisfactory

As seen in the table, the design and layout of the developed enhancement activities in science 9 are found to be very satisfactory for the learners with an overall mean of 3.49. The format in terms of its design and lay out for each topic guides the learners to the appropriateness of the enhancement activities intended for the learners. The findings imply that the enhancement activities in science 9 were found to be accepted with respect to its format as evaluated by the science teachers.

The findings are parallel to the findings of Barasi (2019) in her study entitled "Development, Validation and Acceptability of Computer-Aided Materials in Selected Topics in Elementary Algebra" found out that the developed instructional materials were acceptable in terms of different aspects.

Table 5. *Science Teachers Evaluation on the Developed Enhancement Activities in Science 9 Utilizing Collaborative Approach with Respect to its Presentation and Organization*

<i>Presentation and Organization</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. Presentation is engaging, interesting and understandable.	3.44	Very Satisfactory
2. There is logical and smooth flow of ideas.	3.39	Very Satisfactory
3. Vocabulary level is adapted to target reader's likely experience and level of understanding.	3.28	Very Satisfactory
4. Length of sentences is suited to the comprehension level of the target reader.	3.44	Very Satisfactory
5. Sentences and paragraph structures are varied and interesting to the target reader.	3.67	Very Satisfactory
Overall	3.44	Very Satisfactory

It could be gleaned from the table that the evaluation of the science teachers on the enhancement activities in Science 9 with respect presentation and organization is interpreted as very satisfactory with an overall mean value of 3.44. The developed enhancement activities in grade 9 science utilizing collaborative approach with respect to its presentation and organization were engaging to the learners that helps develop their knowledge and skills in multiple aspects of language and literacy. The findings imply that the presentation and organization play a significant role in the teaching and learning process.

The presentation and organization fully gained parallel with the study of Simui et al. (2017) which focuses on print-based instructional activities available to distance education learners at the University of Zambia.

Table 6. *Science Teachers Evaluation on the Developed Enhancement Activities in Science 9 Utilizing Collaborative Approach with Respect to its Accuracy and Up-To-Datedness of Information*

<i>Accuracy and Up-to-datedness of Information</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. Conceptual errors.	2.61	Present but very minimal minor errors must be fixed.
2. Factual errors.	3.15	Present but very minimal minor errors must be fixed.
3. Grammatical errors.	2.50	Present but very minimal minor errors must be fixed.
Overall	2.75	Present but very minimal minor errors must be fixed.

With regards to accuracy and being up to date, the science teachers looked into the different errors in the materials, most especially in regard to concepts, facts, and grammar. The science teachers found very minimal errors that must be fixed in the concepts, factual and grammatical errors with the mean of 2.61, 3.15, and 2.50 respectively. Findings imply that the use of the developed instructional materials in terms of its accuracy and up-to-datedness of information indicate that there are minimal minor errors to be fixed.

Same result was obtained by O'Donnell (2019). Her material did not contain many errors and obsolete information. It was concluded that the information is new and correct.

Level of Performance of the Grade 9 Learners Before and After Exposure to the Developed Enhancement Activities Utilizing the Collaborative Approach

Based on the data showed on the table, the category determines the percentage composition of a compound given its chemical formula and vice versa got the highest mean score among the six competencies with 10 questions, it got a mean of 3.21 before the learner's exposure to the material and increased to 6.44 after utilizing the enhancement activities. The category explains how the structure of the carbon atom affects the type of bonds it forms came next with 2.42 before and 5.60 after with 8 questions.

Table 7. *Level of Performance of the Grade 9 Learners Before and After Exposure to the Developed Enhancement Activities Utilizing the Collaborative Approach*

Competency	No. of Items	Before			After		
		Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI
1. Explain how the Quantum Mechanical Model of the atom describes the energies and positions of the electrons	9	2.02	1.68	F	7.18	1.00	VS
2. Recognize different types of compounds (ionic or covalent) based on their properties such as melting point, hardness, polarity and electrical and thermal conductivity	5	1.07	1.45	F	4.00	1.03	O
3. Explain how ions are formed	5	1.27	1.07	F	4.18	0.98	O
4. Explain how the structure of the carbon atom affects the type of bonds it forms	8	2.42	1.60	F	5.60	1.04	VS
5. Recognized the general classes and uses of organic compounds	3	1.07	1.03	F	2.67	0.59	O
6. Determine the percentage composition of a compound given its chemical formula and vice versa	10	3.21	1.77	F	6.44	1.27	VS
Total	40	11.06	4.91	F	30.07	3.76	VS

Based on the data showed on the table, the category determines the percentage composition of a compound given its chemical formula and vice versa got the highest mean score among the six competencies with 10 questions, it got a mean of 3.21 before the learner's exposure to the material and increased to 6.44 after utilizing the enhancement activities. The category explains how the structure of the carbon atom affects the type of bonds it forms came next with 2.42 before and 5.60 after with 8 questions.

On the other hand, the performance of the learners of all the competencies before their exposure to the develop material showed high standard deviation, it means that the answers of the learners for all the competencies were scattered and display variations on the number of items. While the learner's performance after got a low standard deviation which means that the data is closed to each other around the mean. It only means that a small standard deviation means that the values are all closely grouped together and therefore more precise. A large standard deviation means the values are not very similar and therefore less precise.

As a result of being exposed to the enhancement activities, the learner appears to have performed at an exceptionally high level. Additionally, it demonstrates how useful the materials are as a tool for assessing learners who are lagging.

Parallel to the study of Cabansag (2014), with the utilization of the developed and validated enhancement tool in Physics revealed that the utilization of the developed and validated enhancement tool is substantially effective in increasing the level of performance of the least performing students of Grade 8.

Significant Difference on the Level of Performance of the Grade 9 Learners Before and After Exposure to the Developed Enhancement Activities Utilizing the Collaborative Approach

Table 8. *Significant Difference on the Level of Performance of the Grade 9 Learners Before and After Exposure to the Developed Enhancement Activities Utilizing the Collaborative Approach*

Competencies	Exposure	Mean	SD	MD	t	df	P-value	HO	VI
1. Explain how the Quantum Mechanical Model of the atom describes the energies and positions of the electrons	Before	2.02	1.68	5.16	11.603	39	.000	R	S
	After	7.18	1.00						
2. Recognize different types of compounds (ionic or covalent) based on their properties, such as melting point, hardness, polarity, and electrical and thermal conductivity	Before	1.07	1.45	2.93	13.065	39	.000	R	S
	After	4.00	1.03						
3. Explain how ions are formed	Before	1.27	1.07	2.91	9.857	39	.000	R	S
	After	4.18	0.98						
4. Explain how the structure of the carbon atom affects the type of bonds it forms	Before	2.42	1.60	3.18	6.568	39	.000	R	S
	After	5.60	1.04						
5. Recognized the general classes and uses of organic compounds	Before	1.07	1.03	1.60	9.704	39	.000	R	S
	After	2.67	0.59						
6. Determine the percentage composition of a compound given its chemical formula and vice versa	Before	3.21	1.77	3.23	9.409	39	.000	R	S
	After	6.44	1.27						
Total	Before	11.06	4.91	19.01	17.974	39	.000	R	S
	After	30.07	3.76						

The result shows that there is significant difference on the level of performance of the grade 9 learners before and after exposure to the developed enhancement activities utilizing the collaborative approach since the computed probability values of 0.000 among all the competencies are lesser than 0.05 level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is rejected which implies that the enhancement activities in grade 9 science utilizing collaborative approach increase the performance of the learners. The results also suggest that designed enhancement activities were effectively used in teaching Science, which contributes to and results in greater comprehension and

performance among the grade 9 students.

Corresponding to the findings of Dela Cruz (2020) in his study Utilization of Enhancement Materials in Finding the Equation of the Line revealed that there was a significant difference between the test's performances of the two groups. It can be deduced that the utilization of Enhancement Activities is an effective tool in mastering the most essential learning competencies in science 9.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The developed enhancement activities for Science 9 utilizing collaborative approach were highly acceptable as evaluated by the science teachers. Hence the material possessed the characteristics of good instructional material although there are minimal errors to be fixed in terms of its accuracy and up-to- datedness of information.

The learner-respondents performed well in the six competencies as reflected on the improvements showed before and after exposure of the material. Mastery can be seen on those improvements.

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